

Synthesis of 3-(*p*-Fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones as Potential Biologically Active Agents[†]

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Different 5-substituted isatins have been condensed with *p*-fluoro benzoic acid hydrazide to furnish 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (I). Similarly, reaction of *N*-methyl-5-substituted isatins with *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide yielded 1-methyl-3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (II). When I were subjected to Mannich reaction 1-aminomethyl-3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (III) were obtained. These compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *B. megaterium*, *X. malvacearum*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* as well as for CNS activity.

ISATINS are known for their antiviral¹, antibacterial^{2,3}, anthelmintic⁴ and herbicidal⁵ properties. In addition, cysticidal⁶, hypotensive responses and anticonvulsant activity⁷ have also been reported in certain isatin derivatives. The antibacterial activity of different benzoic acid hydrazides is well established^{8,9}. Certain organofluorine compounds have been reported as antibacterial^{10,11} and CNS active agents^{12,13}. In view of all these, it was considered of interest to synthesise certain fluorine containing acid hydrazide incorporated isatins and to evaluate them for their antibacterial activity and CNS activity.

For the synthesis of I, II and III, the starting materials, 5-substituted isatins, were prepared via Sandmeyer reaction¹⁴. *p*-Fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide was prepared from the methyl ester of *p*-fluoro benzoic acid and hydrazine hydrate. Condensation of various *p*-substituted isatins with *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide yielded 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (I). I were also prepared successfully by amine exchange reaction i.e., refluxing 5-substituted-3-arylimino-2-indolinones (IV) with *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide. Identity of both the products was checked by tlc, m.p., mixed m.p. and ir data. Mannich condensation on I, obtained via both the routes, yielded the same Mannich base which indicated that I prepared via both the route was the same. Treatment of 5-substituted isatins with dimethyl sulphate in ethanolic potassium hydroxide yielded *N*-methyl-5-substituted-2-indolinones, which on treatment with *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide yielded *N*-methyl-5-substituted-3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinones (II). Mannich condensation of I with amines furnished III. All the synthesised compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Further support for their structures was derived from ir, nmr and mass spectral data. With a view to rule out the possibility of aminomethylation at -NH of benzoylhydrazono group in I during

Mannich condensation, II (R = Cl) was heated with morpholine and formalin. In this reaction II was

recovered unchanged and its identity was established on the basis of m.p., mixed m.p., ir and tlc.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr and were as expected. NMR spectra were taken in CDCl₃ at 90 MHz. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV.

3-(*p*-Fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (I):

Method A: A mixture of isatin (4.4 g; 0.03 mole) and *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide (4.2 g; 0.03 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr in presence of 2-3 drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the solid product was filtered and washed with ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3-(*p*-FLUORO)BENZYLHYDRAZONO-5-SUBSTITUTED-2-INDOLINONES (I)

Sl. No.	R	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
1.	H	78	>270	C ₂₅ H ₁₀ FN ₂ O ₂
2.	OH	75	>260	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ FN ₂ O ₃
3.	Cl	79	>260	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClFN ₂ O ₂
4.	Br	82	>260	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrFN ₂ O ₂

[†] Part XXXIII of the series Potential Biologically Active Agents.

TABLE 3—1-AMINOMETHYL-3-(*p*-FLUORO)BENZOYLHYDRAZONO-5-SUBSTITUTED-2-INDOLINONES (III)

Sl. No.	R	X	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analysis%	
						Calcd.	Found
9.	H	CH ₃	62	268-269	C ₁₁ H ₉ FN ₂ O ₂	N, 14.73	14.48
10.	H	O	65	207-208	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂	C, 62.82 H, 4.97	62.95 5.01
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	63	195-196	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂	C, 67.00 H, 5.83 N, 14.21	66.73 5.51 13.81
12.	CH ₃	O	68	217-218	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂	C, 63.63 H, 5.30	62.98 5.13
13.	Cl	CH ₃	62	190d	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ O ₂	C, 60.79 H, 4.82	60.95 5.45
14.	Cl	O	62	215	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ O ₂	C, 57.62 H, 4.32 N, 13.44	57.80 4.25 13.16
15.	Br	CH ₃	64	197-198	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ BrFN ₂ O ₂	N, 12.20	12.20
16.	Br	O	68	213-214	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ BrFN ₂ O ₂	C, 52.06 H, 3.90 N, 12.14	51.60 3.71 11.88

Mass spectra No. 11 - M⁺, m/e 394
No. 16 - M⁺, m/e 460/462

PMR (δ value) : 15, 1.42 (6H, -CH₂CH₂CH₃ -), 2.26(4H, N<CH₂)
4.35 (2H, N-CH₂N), 6.80-7.40 (4H, ¹J-C₆H₄-F),
7.81-7.96 (3H, remaining¹Ar - H).

Method B : I were also prepared successfully by amine exchange reaction in which 3-arylimino group of 5-substituted-3-arylimino-2-indolinones was replaced by (*p*-fluoro)benzylhydrazono group. 5-Substituted-3-arylimino-2-indolinone (0.005 mole) was refluxed with *p*-fluoro benzoic acid hydrazide (0.005 mole) in ethanol (10 ml) for 6 hr. The solid obtained after cooling the reaction mixture was filtered, washed well with ethanol. Identity of I, prepared by method B, was checked by m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectral data. Identical Mannich bases (III) obtained from I, prepared by methods A and B, further established their identity.

N-Methyl-3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (II) : 3-Chloro-N-methyl-isatin (1.95 g; 0.01 mole) was refluxed with *p*-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide (1.55 g; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) for 4 hr in presence of 2-3 drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the resultant product was filtered, washed well with ethanol and recrystallised from ethyl acetate (Table 2).

TABLE 2—N-METHYL-3-(*p*-FLUORO)BENZOYLHYDRAZONO-5-SUBSTITUTED-2-INDOLINONES (II)

Sl. No.	R	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis%	
					Calcd.	Found
5.	H	69	218-220	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂	C, 64.64 H, 4.04	64.21 3.89
6.	OH	75	206-207	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂	N, 13.50	13.64
7.	Cl	72	203-204	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂	C, 57.91 H, 3.31	57.72 3.31
8.	Br	76	213-214	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ O ₂	N, 12.66 N, 11.17	12.61 10.84

Mass spectra : No. 7 - M⁺, m/e 331/333.

Reaction of II (R-Cl) with morpholine and formalin : II (0.005 mole) (R=Cl) was suspended in 10 ml of warm ethanol. Morpholine (1 ml) and formalin (1 ml) was added and the mixture stirred at 80° for 30 min. Working up the reaction mixture yielded a solid which was recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Its mixed m.p. with compounds 7 showed no depression. The product was identical with compound 7.

1-Amino-3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-5-substituted-2-indolinones (III) : I (0.005 mole) was suspended in 10 ml of ethanol. To this suspension 1 ml of 37% formalin and amine (0.005 mole) were added with vigorous stirring. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 10 min and thereafter allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The product thus deposited was filtered, washed well with ethanol and petroleum ether (60-80°) and dried well in air. It was finally recrystallised from chloroform or carbon tetrachloride and petroleum ether (60-80°) or ethyl acetate (Table 3).

3-Arylimino-2-indolinones (IV) : Isatin (0.01 mole) was taken in 25 ml of absolute ethanol containing 2-3 drops of glacial acetic acid and aryl amine (0.01 mole) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. The product was recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

Pharmacology :

CNS activity : Thirteen compounds out of the 16 synthesised were examined for their toxicity tests and the gross CNS activity at 1/5th of ALD₅₀, by the method of Wiel¹⁵ (Table 4).

The compounds have been found to be non-toxic and psychotropic agents. Compound No. 4

TABLE 4—ONS ACTIVITY

Compound No.	ALD ₅₀	SMA	Gross effect at 1/5th of ALD ₅₀		
			SA Reactivity	Writhing	Body temp.
2	825	—	—	(+)	—
4	681	↓	↓	(+)	0.2°
5	1000	↓	↓	(+)	—
6	1000	—	—	(+)	—
7	681	—	—	(+)	0.2°
8	1000	↑	↑	(-)	(-)
9	1000	↑	↑	(-)	(-)
10	1000	↑	↑	(-)	(-)
11	1000	↑	↑	(-)	(-)
13	1000	↑	↑	(-)	(-)
14	1000	↑	↑	(-)	0.6°
15	681	↑	↑	(-)	0.2°
16	1000	↑	↑	(-)	0.4°

and 5 have been found to be CNS depressant whereas the remaining tested compounds have shown an increase in SMA and reactivity to sound and touch. Compound No. 2 and 4 to 7 have induced writhing, showing some muscle relaxant effect on belly muscles. Compound No. 4, 7 and 14 to 16 have induced hypothermia ranging between 0.2 to 0.6°. Rest of the compounds were ineffective towards body temperature.

Antibacterial activity: The method of Varma and Nobles¹⁶ was employed for determining the antibacterial spectrum of all the compounds. The test organisms included *Bacillus megaterium*, *Xanthomias malvacearium*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Sterile filter paper discs (5 mm diam), saturated with solution of the test compounds

TABLE 5—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	<i>B. mag.</i>	<i>X. m.</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
1.	+	+	+	+
2.	+	++	+	++
3.	++	+++	+	++
4.	+	++	+	+
5.	-	+	+	+
6.	-	+	++	+
7.	+	+	+	+
8.	-	+	+	++
9.	++++	++	+	+
10.	++++	+++	+	+
11.	++	+++	++	+
12.	++	-	-	-
13.	++++	++	+	+
14.	++++	+	-	+
15.	+++	+	-	+
16.	++	-	+	-

- = No inhibition ; + = Zone size 6-8 mm ;
 ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm ; +++ = Zone size 10-15 mm ;
 ++++ = Zone size > 15 mm.

were placed on the agar [1.5% (w/v) agar; 0.5% (w/v) NaCl; 0.5% (w/v) glucose and 2.5% (w/v) peptone, pH 6.8-7.0] plates after drying up the solvent. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hr and zones of inhibition around the discs were measured. Bacterial cultures maintained at Public Analyst Laboratory, U. P. Government, Lucknow, were used (Table 5).

Compound No. 9, 10, 13 and 14 were found to be most active against *B. megaterium* and *X. malvacearium*.

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